

A NEW CLASS OF THE r -STIRLING NUMBERS AND THE GENERALIZED BERNOULLI POLYNOMIALS

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Abstract

The main object of this paper is to express the values at non-negative integers of the generalized Bernoulli polynomials by using a class of the Stirling numbers of the second kind.

1. Introduction

Recall that the r -Stirling number of the second kind, $\left\{ \begin{smallmatrix} n \\ k \end{smallmatrix} \right\}_r$, counts the number of partitions of the set $[n] := \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ into k non-empty subsets such that the elements of the set $[r]$ are in different subsets [3]. These numbers are determined by its generating function to be:

$$\sum_{n \geq k} \left\{ \begin{smallmatrix} n+r \\ k+r \end{smallmatrix} \right\}_r \frac{t^n}{n!} = \frac{1}{k!} (\exp(t) - 1)^k \exp(rt),$$

where $\left\{ \begin{smallmatrix} n \\ k \end{smallmatrix} \right\}_1 = \left\{ \begin{smallmatrix} n \\ k \end{smallmatrix} \right\}_0 := \left\{ \begin{smallmatrix} n \\ k \end{smallmatrix} \right\}$ are the Stirling numbers of the second kind.

In [11], the authors expressed $B_n^{(\alpha)}(\pm r)$ in terms of the r -Stirling numbers of both kinds. In [12], they expressed $B_n^{(\alpha)}\left(\pm \frac{r}{m}\right)$ in terms of the r -Whitney numbers of both kinds, where $B_n^{(\alpha)}(x)$ is the n -th order Bernoulli polynomial (see for example [8, 15]) defined by its exponential generating function to be

$$\sum_{n \geq 0} B_n^{(\alpha)}(x) \frac{t^n}{n!} = \left(\frac{t}{\exp(t) - 1} \right)^\alpha \exp(xt),$$

where $B_n^{(1)}(x) = B_n(x)$ are the classical Bernoulli polynomials.

The generalized Bernoulli polynomials $B_n^{[s-1,\alpha]}(x)$ extend the polynomials introduced by Natalini and Bernardini [13] (see also [6, 2]), and are defined by Kurt [7] (see also [16]) as follows:

$$\sum_{n \geq 0} B_n^{[s-1,\alpha]}(x) \frac{t^n}{n!} = \left(\frac{\frac{t^s}{s!}}{\exp(t) - \sum_{j=0}^{s-1} \frac{t^j}{j!}} \right)^\alpha \exp(xt), \quad s \geq 1. \tag{1}$$

In order to give explicit formulas for these polynomials at non-negative integers, we introduce in this paper a class of the r -Stirling numbers of the second kind which can be viewed as a special case of those given in [10].

Definition 1. For $s \geq 1$, we define the s -quasi-associated r -Stirling numbers of the second kind, denoted by $\left\{ \begin{matrix} n \\ k \end{matrix} \right\}_r^s$, by the number of partitions of an n -set into k blocks such that the first r elements are in different blocks, a block from the other $(k - r)$ -blocks must be of cardinality greater than or equal to s .

Below, we show that the numbers $B_n^{[s-1,\alpha]}(r)$ are linked to these numbers (Theorems 2, 3) by

$$B_n^{[s-1,\alpha]}(r) = \sum_{j=0}^n \binom{n + sj}{n, s, \dots, s}^{-1} \left\{ \begin{matrix} n + sj + r \\ j + r \end{matrix} \right\}_r^{s+1} (-\alpha)_j,$$

$$B_n^{[s-1,\alpha]}(r) = \alpha \binom{\alpha + n}{n} \sum_{j=0}^n (-1)^j \binom{n}{j} \frac{j!}{\alpha + j} \binom{n + sj}{n, s, \dots, s}^{-1} \left\{ \begin{matrix} n + sj + r \\ j + r \end{matrix} \right\}_r^s,$$

where $(x)_n = x(x - 1) \cdots (x - n + 1)$ for $n \geq 1$, $(x)_0 = 1$,

$$\binom{n + sj}{n, s, \dots, s} := \frac{(n + sj)!}{n! (s!)^j}.$$

Before proving these identities, let us give some combinatorial properties of the s -quasi-associated r -Stirling numbers of the second kind defined above.

2. Combinatorial Properties

From the above definition, we may state that

$$\left\{ \begin{matrix} n \\ k \end{matrix} \right\}_r^s = 0, \quad n < sk \text{ or } k < r,$$

$$\left\{ \begin{matrix} 0 \\ k \end{matrix} \right\}_r^s = \delta_{k,0}, \quad k \geq 0,$$

$$\left\{ \begin{matrix} n \\ r \end{matrix} \right\}_r^s = r^{n-r}, \quad n \geq sr.$$

Using combinatorial arguments, we assert that these numbers admit an expression given by the following theorem.

Theorem 1. *For $n \geq sk \geq sr \geq 1$, the s -quasi-associated r -Stirling numbers of the second kind can be written as*

$$\left\{ \begin{matrix} n \\ k \end{matrix} \right\}_r^s = \frac{(n-r)!}{(k-r)!} \sum_{n_1+\dots+n_k=n-r-s(k-r)} \frac{1}{n_1! \cdots n_r! (n_{r+1}+s)! \cdots (n_k+s)!}.$$

Proof. To partition a set $[n]$ into k blocks B_1, \dots, B_k such that every block does not contain any element of $[r]$, must be of cardinality greater than or equal to s . The first r elements are in different blocks (of cardinalities not less than 1), let the elements of $[r]$ be in different blocks B_1, \dots, B_r . So, there are $\frac{1}{(k-r)!} \binom{n-r}{n_1, \dots, n_k} := \frac{(n-r)!}{(k-r)! n_1! \cdots n_k!}$ ways to choose n_1, \dots, n_k in $[n] \setminus [r]$ such that

- $n_1 \geq 0, \dots, n_r \geq 0 : n_1, \dots, n_r$ are, respectively, in B_1, \dots, B_r ,
- $n_{r+1} \geq s, \dots, n_k \geq s : n_{r+1}, \dots, n_k$ are, respectively, in B_{r+1}, \dots, B_k .

Then the total number of these partitions is:

$$\begin{aligned} \left\{ \begin{matrix} n \\ k \end{matrix} \right\}_r^s &= \frac{1}{(k-r)!} \sum_{n_1+\dots+n_k=n-r, n_{r+1} \geq s, \dots, n_k \geq s} \binom{n-r}{n_1, \dots, n_k} \\ &= \frac{(n-r)!}{(k-r)!} \sum_{n_1+\dots+n_k=n-r-s(k-r)} \frac{1}{n_1! \cdots n_r! (n_{r+1}+s)! \cdots (n_k+s)!}. \end{aligned}$$

□

By a simple manipulation of Theorem 1, we may state the following.

Corollary 1. *The s -quasi-associated r -Stirling numbers of the second kind have generating function*

$$\sum_{n \geq k} \left\{ \begin{matrix} n+r \\ k+r \end{matrix} \right\}_r^s \frac{t^n}{n!} = \frac{1}{k!} \left(\sum_{i \geq s} \frac{t^i}{i!} \right)^k \exp(rt).$$

Using combinatorial arguments, we give below three recurrence relations.

Proposition 1. *For $n > sr \geq 1$ we have*

$$\left\{ \begin{matrix} n \\ k \end{matrix} \right\}_r^s = k \left\{ \begin{matrix} n-1 \\ k \end{matrix} \right\}_r^s + \binom{n-r-1}{s-1} \left\{ \begin{matrix} n-s \\ k-1 \end{matrix} \right\}_r^s.$$

Proof. To partition the set $[n]$ into k blocks such that every block from the $[n] \setminus [r]$ must be of cardinality greater than or equal to s and the elements of $[r]$ must be in different blocks, we separate the element n and proceed as follows:

(a) If n is in a block intersecting $[r]$, there are $\left\{ \begin{smallmatrix} n-1 \\ k \end{smallmatrix} \right\}_r^s$ ways to partition the set $[n-1]$ into k blocks with the same conditions. The element n (not really used) can be inserted in the r blocks which intersect $[r]$, so we count $r \left\{ \begin{smallmatrix} n-1 \\ k \end{smallmatrix} \right\}_r^s$ ways.

(b) If n is in a block of cardinality s and does not intersect $[r]$, there are $\binom{n-r-1}{s-1}$ ways to choose $s-1$ elements to be with this element in the same block. The remaining $n-s$ elements can be partitioned into $k-1$ blocks in $\left\{ \begin{smallmatrix} n-s \\ k-1 \end{smallmatrix} \right\}_r^s$ ways. So, the number of ways in this case must be $\binom{n-r-1}{s-1} \left\{ \begin{smallmatrix} n-s \\ k-1 \end{smallmatrix} \right\}_r^s$.

(c) If n is in a block of cardinality $\geq s+1$ and does not intersect $[r]$, there are $(k-r) \left\{ \begin{smallmatrix} n-1 \\ k \end{smallmatrix} \right\}_r^s$ ways. Thus, the number of all partitions is given by $\left\{ \begin{smallmatrix} n \\ k \end{smallmatrix} \right\}_r^s = r \left\{ \begin{smallmatrix} n-1 \\ k \end{smallmatrix} \right\}_r^s + \binom{n-r-1}{s-1} \left\{ \begin{smallmatrix} n-s \\ k-1 \end{smallmatrix} \right\}_r^s + (k-r) \left\{ \begin{smallmatrix} n-1 \\ k \end{smallmatrix} \right\}_r^s$. \square

Proposition 2. For $r \geq 1$ we have

$$\left\{ \begin{smallmatrix} n \\ k \end{smallmatrix} \right\}_r^s = \sum_{j \geq 0} \binom{n-r}{j} \left\{ \begin{smallmatrix} n-1-j \\ k-1 \end{smallmatrix} \right\}_{r-1}^s.$$

Proof. To partition the set $[n]$ into k blocks such that the first r -elements are in different blocks and every block does not intersect $[r]$ must be of cardinality greater than or equal to s , we operate as follows:

The element r can be in a block of cardinality $j+1$ in $\binom{n-r}{j} \left\{ \begin{smallmatrix} n-1-j \\ k-1 \end{smallmatrix} \right\}_{r-1}^s$ ways, so we illustrate two cases,

(a) The number of ways for choosing the j elements between $(n-1) - (r-1)$ elements of $[n] \setminus [r]$ to be in the same block with the element r is $\binom{n-r}{j}$,

(b) The number of ways to partition the remaining $n - (j+1) = n-1-j$ elements into $k-1$ blocks such that every block does not intersect $[r]$, must be of cardinality greater than or equal to s , and the elements of $[r-1]$ are in different blocks is $\left\{ \begin{smallmatrix} n-1-j \\ k-1 \end{smallmatrix} \right\}_{r-1}^s$. \square

3. Application to the Generalized Bernoulli Polynomials

We give in this section two expressions in terms of the s -quasi-associated r -Stirling numbers of the second kind for $B_n^{[s-1, \alpha]}(r)$. The following theorem gives a simplified expression for $B_n^{[s-1, \alpha]}(r)$ for all non-negative integers r .

Theorem 2. We have

$$B_n^{[s-1, \alpha]}(r) = \sum_{j=0}^n \binom{n+sj}{n, s, \dots, s}^{-1} \left\{ \begin{smallmatrix} n+sj+r \\ j+r \end{smallmatrix} \right\}_r^{s+1} (-\alpha)_j$$

for a non-positive integer α , where $\alpha = -k$. We also have

$$B_n^{[s-1,-k]}(r) = k! \binom{n+sk}{n,s,\dots,s}^{-1} \left\{ \begin{matrix} n+sk+r \\ k+r \end{matrix} \right\}_r^s.$$

Proof. From the definition of $B_n^{[s-1,\alpha]}(x)$, we get

$$\sum_{n \geq 0} B_n^{[s-1,\alpha]}(r) \frac{t^n}{n!} = \left(\sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \binom{j+s}{s}^{-1} \frac{t^j}{j!} \right)^{-\alpha} \exp(rt) = \exp(rt) \sum_{n \geq 0} f_n(-\alpha) \frac{t^n}{n!},$$

which gives $B_n^{[s-1,\alpha]}(r) = \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} r^{n-k} f_k(-\alpha)$, where $(f_n(x))$ is a sequence of binomial type with $f_n(1) = \binom{n+s}{s}^{-1}$. Use the known relation (see [14])

$$f_n(-\alpha) = \sum_{j=0}^n B_{n,j} \left(\binom{i+s}{s}^{-1} \right) (-\alpha)_j$$

to obtain

$$B_n^{[s-1,\alpha]}(r) = \sum_{j=0}^n (-\alpha)_j \sum_{k=j}^n \binom{n}{k} r^{n-k} B_{k,j} \left(\binom{i+s}{s}^{-1} \right),$$

where $B_{n,k}(x_i) := B_{n,k}(x_1, x_2, \dots)$ is the partial Bell polynomial, see [1, 4, 9].

Now, the exponential generating function of

$$A(n, j) := \sum_{k=j}^n \binom{n}{k} r^{n-k} B_{k,j} \left(\binom{i+s}{s}^{-1} \right)$$

must be

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n \geq j} A(n, j) \frac{t^n}{n!} &= \exp(rt) \sum_{k \geq j} B_{k,j} \left(\binom{i+s}{s}^{-1} \right) \frac{t^k}{k!} \\ &= \frac{1}{j!} \left(\sum_{i \geq 1} \frac{s! t^i}{(i+s)!} \right)^j \exp(rt) \\ &= \frac{t^{-sj}}{j!} \left(s! \sum_{i \geq s+1} \frac{t^i}{i!} \right)^j \exp(rt) \\ &= \sum_{n \geq j} \frac{(s!)^j n!}{(n+sj)!} \left\{ \begin{matrix} n+sj+r \\ j+r \end{matrix} \right\}_r^{s+1} \frac{t^n}{n!}, \end{aligned}$$

So, we obtain

$$A(n, j) = \frac{n!(s!)^j}{(n + sj)!} \left\{ \begin{matrix} n + sj + r \\ j + r \end{matrix} \right\}_r^{s+1} \quad \text{and} \quad B_n^{[s-1, \alpha]}(r) = \sum_{j=0}^n A(n, j) (-\alpha)_j.$$

The second part of the theorem follows from the expansion

$$\sum_{n \geq 0} B_n^{[s-1, -k]}(r) \frac{t^n}{n!} = t^{-sk} (s!)^k \left(\sum_{i \geq s} \frac{t^i}{i!} \right)^k \exp(rt) = k! t^{-sk} \sum_{n \geq sk} \left\{ \begin{matrix} n + r \\ k + r \end{matrix} \right\}_r^s \frac{t^n}{n!}.$$

□

The next corollary is a particular case from Theorem 2.

Corollary 2. *We have*

$$B_n^{(\alpha)}(r) := B_n^{[0, \alpha]}(r) = \sum_{j=0}^n \frac{n!}{(n + j)!} \left\{ \begin{matrix} n + j + r \\ j + r \end{matrix} \right\}_r^2 (-\alpha)_j.$$

So, the values of the Bernoulli polynomials at non-negative integers are given by

$$B_n(r) := B_n^{(1)}(r) = \sum_{j=0}^n (-1)^j \binom{n + j}{j}^{-1} \left\{ \begin{matrix} n + j + r \\ j + r \end{matrix} \right\}_r^2,$$

and from the known identity $B_n^{(n+1)}(x) = (x - 1)^n$, we may state that for $\alpha = n + 1$ we have

$$\sum_{j=0}^n (-1)^j \left\{ \begin{matrix} n + j + r \\ j + r \end{matrix} \right\}_r^2 = (r - 1)^n.$$

Other expressions in terms of the s -quasi-associated r -Stirling numbers of the second kind for $B_n^{[s-1, \alpha]}(r)$ are given as follows.

Theorem 3. *Let p, r, n, s be non-negative integers such that $s \geq 1, p \geq n$. Then we have*

$$B_n^{[s-1, \alpha]}(r) = \alpha \binom{\alpha + p}{p} \sum_{j=0}^p (-1)^j \binom{p}{j} \frac{j!}{\alpha + j} \binom{n + sj}{n, s, \dots, s}^{-1} \left\{ \begin{matrix} n + sj + r \\ j + r \end{matrix} \right\}_r^s,$$

where

$$\binom{x}{k} := \frac{(x)_k}{k!}.$$

Proof. For any polynomial f of degree $n \leq p$, Melzak's formula [5] gives

$$f(x + \alpha) = \alpha \binom{\alpha + p}{p} \sum_{j=0}^p (-1)^j \binom{p}{j} \frac{f(x - j)}{\alpha + j},$$

where $\binom{x}{n} = \frac{x^n}{n!}$. By Theorem 2, we deduce that $B_n^{[s-1,\alpha]}(x)$ is a polynomial in α of degree at most n . Then by setting $f(x) = B_n^{[s-1,x]}(r)$ in Melzak's Formula we obtain

$$B_n^{[s-1,\alpha]}(r) = \alpha \binom{\alpha+p}{p} \sum_{j=0}^p (-1)^j \binom{p}{j} \frac{B_n^{[s-1,-j]}(r)}{\alpha+j}.$$

The desired identity follows by using the second identity of Theorem 2, □

Where $p = n$ in Theorem 3 we get the following corollary,

Corollary 3. *We have*

$$B_n^{[s-1,\alpha]}(r) = \alpha \binom{\alpha+n}{n} \sum_{j=0}^n (-1)^j \binom{n}{j} \frac{j!}{\alpha+j} \binom{n+sj}{n,s,\dots,s}^{-1} \left\{ \begin{matrix} n+sj+r \\ j+r \end{matrix} \right\}_r^s.$$

This gives the values of the high order Bernoulli polynomials at non-negative integers to be

$$B_n^{(\alpha)}(r) := B_n^{[0,\alpha]}(r) = \alpha \binom{\alpha+n}{n} \sum_{j=0}^n \frac{(-1)^j}{\alpha+j} \frac{\binom{n}{j}}{\binom{n+j}{j}} \left\{ \begin{matrix} n+j+r \\ j+r \end{matrix} \right\}_r.$$

So, the values of the Bernoulli polynomials at non-negative integers are given by

$$B_n(r) = \sum_{j=0}^n (-1)^j \frac{\binom{n+1}{j+1}}{\binom{n+j}{j}} \left\{ \begin{matrix} n+j+r \\ j+r \end{matrix} \right\}_r.$$

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